

**INTERPHASE EFFECTS ON THE ELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF
COMPOSITE MATERIALS :
THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was conducted to establish the effect of an interphase on the elastic behavior of an E-glass fiber/epoxy unidirectional composite. Indeed, the numerical and experimental results show that the structure and properties of this region have a major role on the performance of composite materials. The numerical data are in good agreement with measured transverse Young's modulus. Then the homogenization technique was mainly focused on the evaluation of interphase properties. An inverse analysis was conducted to evaluate interphase characteristics by means of experimental moduli of composite materials. However at present, it is only a comparative method between several kinds of interphase.

Keywords : E-glass unidirectional composite, Homogenization techniques, Interphase

1. INTRODUCTION

Most of the early micromechanical modeling techniques for describing composite elastic behavior consider the composite material as a two phase medium with a perfect interface. However, the actual situation is more complicated. Indeed, many studies [1,2] on polymeric matrix composites have suggested that a volume of material surrounding the fiber is significantly different from the bulk matrix. Thus, composite materials must be considered as consisting of three phases: the fiber, the matrix and an area of "disturbed" matrix, surrounding each inclusion. This last medium is called *interphase*.

Numerous reasons can be enumerated to explain matrix modifications. For instance, surface treatment or fiber coating can give rise to a structurally different zone, and the cross-link density of the polymeric net and the macromolecular mobility can be modified in the vicinity of the fiber. The

growing experimental evidence of the physical and chemical structure of interfacial areas leads to the conclusion that the fiber create a complex region not easily amenable to predictive analysis. Moreover, because of the geometrical situation of the interphase between fiber and matrix and its similarity with the matrix, its elastic properties and dimension are unknown. Direct measurement have not been found to characterize accurately this interphase.

The objective of the present work is twofold:

First, we will show that the interphase region can have a profound effect on the elastic properties of unidirectional composite material.

Second, we will demonstrate that a homogenization method could be a useful tool to evaluate the Young's modulus and dimension of interphase.

2. HOMOGENEIZATION TECHNIQUES

The theory, which has been used for analysis of interphase effect, is based on homogenization techniques, and especially the periodic structure homogenisation (noted PSH) [3, 4, 5]. First, we will present some of the basic features of this method. Then we will display our developments for unidirectional composites.

The different homogenization techniques enable us to evaluate the overall properties of heterogeneous materials, in terms of constituent characteristics. The base of every homogenization approach is as follows:

- Choose a microscopic volume in material, which could be a representative elementary volume (noted RVE).
- Subject the RVE to an average strain (respectively stress) with appropriate boundary conditions.
- Calculate the average stress (resp. strain) on the RVE.
- Calculate, from the relation between average strain and stress, the overall elastic moduli of the composite material.

Figure 1 : Axis definition

The coordinate system for the the composite is shown in figure 1.

The PSH method assumes mechanical and geometrical periodicity of the microscopic structure. With this specific space distribution, the prediction of effective properties means solving a

mechanical problem with unusual boundary conditions. Indeed, the direct consequence is that the stress vector must be antiperiodic on the RVE boundary and displacement must decay in two terms : a linear and a periodic term.

$$u_i = \tilde{u}_i + E_{ij} x_j \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{u}_i is periodic over the RVE.

Unidirectional composite are generally assumed to be transversely isotropic. Likewise, the strain and stress are assumed to be constant along fiber axis.

This implies the following relation :

$$\tilde{u}_i = \tilde{u}_i (y_1, y_2) \quad (2)$$

and

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_{33} = 0 ; \tilde{\epsilon}_{31} = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{u}_{3,1} ; \tilde{\epsilon}_{32} = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{u}_{3,2} \quad (3)$$

Hence, the matrix problem formulation is :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{31} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{1111} & c_{1122} & c_{1133} & & & \\ c_{2211} & c_{2222} & c_{2233} & & & \\ c_{3311} & c_{3322} & c_{3333} & & & \\ & & & c_{1212} & & \\ 0 & & & & c_{2323} & \\ & & & & & c_{3131} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\epsilon}_{11} + E_{11} \\ \tilde{\epsilon}_{22} + E_{22} \\ 0 + E_{33} \\ 2\tilde{\epsilon}_{12} + 2E_{12} \\ \tilde{u}_{3,2} + 2E_{23} \\ \tilde{u}_{3,1} + 2E_{31} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

\tilde{u}_{y_1} and \tilde{u}_{y_2} dependent
 \tilde{u}_{y_3} dependent

These local relations as well as the resulting orthotropic form of the macroscopic material show the decomposition of the global 3-D problem in two kinds of 2-D problems : A generalized plane strain problem (noted P1) and (ii) an anti-plane problem (noted P2).

The final matrix formulation is :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & S_m \langle \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \rangle \\ S_m \langle \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \rangle & S_m \langle \mathbf{D} \rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \\ \mathbf{E}_i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ S_m \Sigma_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where :

$$- \langle \mathbf{A} \rangle = \frac{1}{S_m} \int_{S_m} \mathbf{A} \, dS$$

- D is the reduced Hooke's tensor,
- S_m is the R.V.E surface,
- \mathbf{K} is the common rigidity matrix.

with :

- $\Sigma = \{\Sigma_{11}, \Sigma_{22}, \Sigma_{33}, \Sigma_{12}\}^T$ and $E = \{E_{11}, E_{22}, E_{33}, 2E_{12}\}^T$ in the case of the generalized plane strain problem,

- $\Sigma = \{\Sigma_{23}, \Sigma_{31}\}^T$ and $E = \{2E_{23}, 2E_{31}\}^T$ for the antiplane problem.

The finite element form of the generalized plane strain problem includes two periodic degrees of freedom by node (\tilde{u}_1 and \tilde{u}_2) and the anti-plane problem involves only one periodic degree of freedom by node (\tilde{u}_3).

The solution of the P1 problem yields the following effective properties : $E_1 = E_t$, $G_{12} = G_{tt}$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{tt}$ and $E_3 = E_l$. The second problem gives $G_{31} = G_{lt}$.

3. COMPUTATION OF HOMOGENEIZATION RESULTS

Because of the transversely isotropic behavior which is assumed here, the numerical calculations are carried out for a hexagonal basic cell. A computer program has been written to solve the mechanical problem of the PSH method. The numerical solution uses the finite element method (noted FEM). The finite element mesh created, contains 768 3-noded *isoparametric*, triangular elements. The typical mesh is illustrated in Figure 2. Obviously, the choice of mesh density is a compromise between accuracy and computation time.

Figure 2. Finite element model for numerical homogenization

3-1 Effect of interphase on elastic behavior of unidirectional composites

In a previous paper [6] we showed numerically the effect of interphase on elastic properties of unidirectional composites. One of the most sensitive to the interphase presence is the transverse

Young's modulus. The following numerical and experimental comparison relies on E_t , because of its sensitivity and how easy it is measured experimentally.

3-1-1 Interphase Modeling

In this present study, we assume the interphase to be an axisymmetric region of uniform and fixed dimensions and mechanical properties. The actual interphase must be an area of radially varying properties and must also exhibit a circumferential properties gradient. However we haven't enough experimental information on interphase. Therefore, we consider an interphase model with average and uniform modulus.

We have assumed that interphase is based on diffusion processes of the polymeric sizing agent (on the fiber) inside the epoxy matrix. The interphase is the result of the intermixing phenomena and migration of coupling agents inside matrix. Consequently, the dimension of the interphase area depends only on the diffusion coefficient C_0 of the coating inside the matrix. The interphase thickness was evaluated from the fiber coating quantity and the diffusion coefficient. An approximative elastic modulus of the interphase model was obtained with a bending test on samples of mixtures of coating agents and epoxy matrix. The coating volume ratio was given by the coefficient C_0 . Experimental results are shown in table 2. We notice that the Young's modulus of such samples is higher than the epoxy matrix ones. These experimental data must be considered as a first approximation of interphase.

3-1-2 Numerical and experimental results

In order to illustrate the application of the present approach, two composites have been selected with different industrial fiber sizing. The material properties used in the calculation, representative of E-glass fiber and epoxy matrix, are listed as follows.

Material	E(GPa)	ν
E-glass-fiber	73	0,22
Epoxy resin	2,9	0,40

Table 1: Epoxy-matrix and E-glass fiber properties

The interphase characteristics are resumed in table 2.

Interphase	E_i (GPa)	e_i (μm) (estimated)
I ₁	3,6	0,84
I ₂	3,6	0,42

Table 2 : interphase "model" characteristics

Material System	Fiber volume ratio (%)	Interphase thickness (μm)	Experimental transverse Young's modulus (GPa)	Numerical transverse Young's modulus (GPa)
I ₁	47,7	0,84	8,89	8,57
I ₂	46,2	0,42	8,11	8,10

Table 3 : Numerical and experimental results

The experimental and numerical results are displayed in table 3.

First, it can be noticed that interphase has a considerable effect on the measured data. Indeed, for similar volume fraction, the Young's moduli are different by about 10%.

The numerical data are in relatively good agreement with experimental moduli. The deviations between measured and numerical moduli are less than 5 %. However, we need further information about interphase to improve our model and agreement between numerical and experimental moduli. Indeed interphase is a more complicated area, it can include impurities, unreacted polymer components and interphase is subjected to residual thermal stresses... Moreover the fiber presence can change the curing cycle [7] and the whole matrix could be affected. Thus the matrix properties in composite can be modified.

4. INVERSE PROBLEM

The problem consist of determining the Young's modulus and the thickness of the interphase, according to experimental transverse elastic modulus of composite materials.

Indeed, the experimental determination or evaluation of interphase elastic modulus is a very complex problem. For instance some studies [8,9] have suggested the interphase is softer than the matrix. On the other hand, Drzal's observations [2] show a more rigid interphase than matrix in bulk.

One way to evaluate numerically the interphase properties is to iterate the mechanical and geometrical interphase characteristics until the homogenised results (numerical data) converge to match the corresponding experimental modulus.

More specifically, a numerical method is used for calculating the dimension and Young's modulus of the interphase, assuming that both matrix, fiber and interphase are homogeneous, linear elastic and isotropic.

As part of the solution of the inverse problem, the homogeneization approach is used to solve a series of direct problems. However the uniqueness of the solution is not guaranteed. Indeed, there is an infinity of solutions (E_i, e_i), where E_i and e_i are respectively the interphase elastic modulus and its thickness. Thus, for a given interphase dimension, the homogeneization process is iterated for several interphase elastic moduli, until the experimental value is obtained. In fact, considering the experimental uncertainty, we take the two experimental bounds of composite modulus ($E+\Delta E$ and $E-\Delta E$). Thus, an upper and lower bound is obtained for the interphase modulus. The same inverse problem is solved for another interphase thickness and so on. The objective is to delimitate the space

of allowable solutions (E_i , e_i). To demonstrate the effectiveness and limitations of the solution procedure, two applications are presented. The properties of the two composite constituents and fiber coatings are summarized in table 4. We used two simplified polymeric sizings which can be considered as sizing model for epoxy matrix.

Material System	Fiber volume ratio (%)	Surface treatment	E_t (GPa)
C1	58.9	Epoxy coating with silane compatible with epoxy resin	15.08 ± 0.10
C2	61.0	PVAc coating incompatible with epoxy resin (with silane)	14.65 ± 0.36

Table 4 : Composite characteristics

The allowable solution space for these two composites are presented in figures 3 and 4. This domain is too large and does not give accurate information. But some simple physical and chemical considerations could limit this domain. For instance, diffusion coefficients could give an upper and a lower limit for interphase dimension.

Figure 3 : Space of admissible values for composite C1

Figure 4 : Space of admissible values for composite C2

We notice that for a thickness located between 0.5 and 1 μm , the elastic modulus of interphase C1 is higher than for interphase C2. Indeed the allowable domain is as follows:

- Composite C1, if $0.8 \mu\text{m} \leq e_i \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$
 $7.6 \text{ GPa} \leq E_i \leq 12.8 \text{ GPa}$
- Composite C2, if $0.5 \mu\text{m} \leq e_i \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$
 $3.3 \text{ GPa} \leq E_i \leq 5.2 \text{ GPa}$

These results seem to be consistent with the average elastic coefficients of epoxy (with silane) and PVAc material (with silane). However, we notice that the dimensions of the allowable solution space strongly depend on the experimental uncertainty on the transverse Young's modulus.

Finally, the results presented here indicate that it is possible to develop a predictive method for interphase elastic modulus, based on the homogenization method.

5. CONCLUSION

There are various conclusions which can be drawn as a result of the present work. First, with the simple assumption that interphase properties mainly depend on interdiffusion processes, the numerical results show a major effect of interphase on effective properties of composite materials. Furthermore the numerical/experimental comparison shows a good agreement, in spite of simplistic interphase modeling.

On the other hand, the PSH method seems to be an efficient tool to evaluate interphase properties. Indeed, this technique could be used to solve an inverse problem involving finding the

unknown properties of interphase in terms of experimental results on composite materials. The interphase Young's modulus, which has been obtained for two actual composite systems, seems to be realistic, if we consider a thickness between 0.5 and 1 μm . Other complementary investigations could limit this solution domain (E_i , e_i). If the interphase thickness can be evaluated from an experimental investigation, this last method could be used to compute the elastic modulus. Given that no direct experiment has been found for the measure of elastic moduli and dimension of interphase, this method is of great interest. However, at present, more correlations need to be made and more experimental information about interphase and bulk matrix in composite are necessary.

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